

THE LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN “ON THE STATE LANGUAGE”

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Annotation

In this article, the state language policy in the late 1980s in the region of Uzbekistan, the need to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language" and its historical sources, the advantages and disadvantages of the previous law, the most important changes in the subsequent edition, the importance of this law in the development the state language has been discussed and discussed.

Key words: national language, state language, international language, diaspora language, language of national minorities, state language policy, Law "On State Language", line of ancestors, language development.

The first law adopted in Uzbekistan for the revival of national identity and the restoration of the national language in Uzbekistan and which opened the first doors for the independence of the state is considered the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the State language”. Each law is a Measure-a state document adopted to achieve noble goals, and the purpose of the adoption of the language law is, first of all, to ensure the rights to reproduce the Uzbek national language, the freedom of each people and nation to use their native language. Because in a multinational state, the activism of languages is even more pronounced, creating conditions for their preservation and development is one of the important state riddles and issues. Therefore, the state tries to regulate and regulate the languages used on the territory of the country through the law. The situation with languages in Uzbek society is different: the languages of the indigenous peoples and the diaspora or the languages of Sernuf and little languages. Their status in society is also assessed differently.

Russian should be noted that from the first years of the formation of the Soviet-Socialist Republic of Uzbekistan and even before that on the territory of Turkestan, thanks to the Russian invaders, the position of the Russian language was expanded, and the social functions of the national languages were limited to the Uzbek jumala. Therefore, intellectuals of the same period aspired to the permanence of the national language, and their humanistic and nationalistic views were not predators of that time. In particular, Mahmudhoja Behbaja stressed that “... Turkish people need to know Turkish, Persian, Arabic”[1]. Abdullah Avloni, on the other hand, in his work “Turkish Gulistn” presents the national language and literature as a mirror of life and a symbol of the existence of the nation, emphasizing that: “the loss of the national language is the loss of the spirit of the nation. We Turkestanis forget and lose day after day, instead of preserving the national language. And again we are missing half of our language, conquered by Arabic and Persian, and we join the Russians. That's right, we need to know the language of our

government, Russian, like Oshu bread, but it needs to be applied at the proper level... their mixing sucks out the spirit of the language”[2].

Despite all efforts, the Government of that period takes appropriate decisions to improve the social status and social functions of the national language, these decisions led to the execution of the decree of the law. In particular, on December 12, 1923, the Central Executive Committee of the RSFSR made a decision “on the translation of documents into the indigenous languages of the Turkish republics”. In the decision of the Revolutionary Committee of the Uzbek SSR of December 31, 1924, it was emphasized that: “... in volosts and counties, office work should be carried out only in the Uzbek language”. Even this decision approves the rules for hiring and firing local workers in the national language. On July 26, 1925 (No. 6398), the Uzbek decision of the Central Commission came into force, which notes the registration of documents in Uzbek and Russian[3]. With this decision, threats in the Uzbek language began, and in other decisions on the national-Marxist apparatuses of the Uzbek SSR, such threats continued, "the national stage in the Uzbek SSR, as in other republics, has been stopped by the center, and this issue is declared a phenomenon of “bourgeois nationalism.” Since the thirties, the new Russian stage will be further strengthened”. With this decision, threats in the Uzbek language began, and in other decisions on the national-Marxist apparatuses of the Uzbek SSR, such threats continued, "the national stage in the Uzbek SSR, as in other republics, has been stopped by the center, and this issue is declared a phenomenon of “bourgeois nationalism.” Since the thirties, the new Russian stage will be further strengthened " [4, p.70], its negative results still hinder the development of the Uzbek language.

It should be noted that in the Constitution of the USSR, adopted in 1924, the state language is not mentioned in a separate paragraph, but is expressed in an article devoted to the designation of the country. The 1936 Constitution mentions for the first time the term “the language of the universal republics or the language of the region”. In the 1977 Constitution, the term “language of autonomous districts”, “the language of the majority of the population of this territory” was added to the higher term [5].

In the early 1990s, despite the fact that national languages were proclaimed and recognized as the state language in most of the subordinate republics, on May 6, 1990, the “law on the languages of the USSR” was adopted, defining the role of national languages on a disparate scale of the country. Because most of the politicians of that time in the center of the country did not want to believe that the life of this superpower was also coming to an end.

In the first years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, during the transition period, it can be said that there were many mysteries in all spheres of the newly created state. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on December 8, 1992 through a national referendum, defines the structure of statehood in society, simultaneously regulates the development of other branches of the national economy, defines legal norms and, in particular, its 4th article states that “the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the Uzbek language” [6, p. 4]. The mention of this clause in the Constitution is certainly not unreasonable, since language is an instrument that ensures

national unity. The Law of the Uzbek SSR "On the State language" on the basis of the law "On amendments to the Constitution of the Uzbek SSR" dated September 30, 1991 under the number 361-XII was also edited that the phrase "Uzbek SSR" was replaced by the phrase "Republic of Uzbekistan".

Since time and language are in constant contact, the changes taking place in the political, socio-economic life of society are reflected in the language, and there is a need to make additions and changes to the laws to ensure the further development of society. In the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, both to regulate the position of languages and to make the functions of the state language and other national languages more specific, it became necessary to revise the law "On the State language" and revise this Law on the basis of the law "On Amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the State Language", under 167-1, since October 21, 1995. This law refers to the expression of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov: "in establishing the authenticity and fundamental rights of the native language, in gaining a vital position of authentic Uzbek customs and national values, it plays an important role in raising people's spirits" [7, p. 6-7]. Of course, any law that contributes to the material and spiritual benefit of the people is welcomed by society, enjoys support and support and does not pose problems in its observance and execution.

The most important changes that were made to the Law of the Uzbek Republic "On the State Language" in the 1995 edition are that more attention is paid to the language and style of the State, since "any law that is not exhaustive in terms of language and style cannot fulfill its goals and objectives, along with legal reputation" [8, p.4]. The advantages of the new edition are once again manifested in the fact that from the point of view of content and content it has been formed and significantly updated, and from the point of view of language and style -simplified and concise. The law of the time of independence was completely created, that is, it was freed from Soviet ideology, overshadowed by the ideas of national independence, the interests of the state language - the Uzbek language - were objectively expressed.

It should be noted that sometimes in the works of normative documents, the press and speech, the name of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State language" is also incorrectly written and pronounced ("Uzbekistan Republic of Dalat tili hakida"gi law). That is, the word "hakida" is replaced by the word "turisida". Although these words may be synonymous in such a case, the name of the law should not be flexible. The main aspects of editing the law on the person "On the State language" can be traced in the following paragraphs:

The previous law consists of 30 articles, and its later version consists of 24 articles. The introduction, consisting of 7 paragraphs in the previous law and in which the communist ideology was expressed, is abbreviated in this edition, which is an introduction

similar to the explanatory line in which this thing is unacceptable in the construction of laws, and some of the necessary elements of this introduction were squeezed into various articles.

Article 1 states: 1-article. The state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan is Uzbek[9]. In the first legal paragraph, the same meaning was previously expressed, 4 more paragraphs came to a footnote to this paragraph. The annotation of the first paragraph in separate paragraphs is not specific to spelling, but the interpretation of the law in another document is considered. The first article of the previous law has been reduced in volume and meets the requirements of legality. The same 4 subsequent paragraphs of the first law are an expression of Soviet ideology. For example, in the third paragraph it was said: "Russian Russian" appropriate conditions will be created for the development of the national and Russian, Russian and national languages" [9]. This paragraph is a requirement for the development of bilingualism and contradicts the meaning of the first paragraph. This means not limiting the social functions of the Russian language and keeping it in its status. That is, at the time of the adoption of the law, Russian representatives sought not only to preserve the position of the Russian language, but also to create for themselves the legal basis for creating even more favorable conditions.

In the article 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 17, 21, 23, 27- that is, the previous law can be said that the equality of the Russian language in the state language is observed – in Uzbek. These articles indicate that the Uzbek language is officially declared the state language, is not exempt from the registration of the Russian language, and the method of baseness is very weak in the previous law. The content of these articles did not correspond to democratic principles and after gaining independence completely lost its essence. Because there are more than 130 peoples and nationalities living in Uzbekistan, and granting more privileges to the Russian language alone cannot be weighed fairly. In addition to Russian, Karakalpak, Kazakh, Tajik, Tatar, and Turkmen languages were active in the society and could perform the functions of an intermillion language. Therefore, in the new edition, none of these languages was assigned an interethnic status, and even the term "international language" was excluded from the law, and the fourth paragraph of the third article mentions: "citizens have the right to choose the language of interethnic interaction at will" [9].

In the previous law, the attitude to the language of other peoples living in Uzbekistan was abstractly expressed in several articles (1,3,5,6,7,10,13,14,17,18,20,22,25,26). The 1995 edition specifically states in the first paragraph of article 4: "to study the State language in the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens will be provided with conditions and respect for the language of the nation and peoples living on its territory, and conditions will be created for the development of these languages. According to industry researcher Nusratullo Jumakhudzha, "the disadvantage

of the language of laws is their multi-family nature." [10, p.51]. According to this researcher, the above text can be even shorter without changing the meaning, and one of the requirements of legality is the expression of the material in both specific words and sentences. He also offers several edits of his own, which can be taken into account in the next editions of this law.

The third paragraph of article 4 of the 1989 Law on the study of the State Language states: "in the Uzbek SSR, education and teaching of the state language are provided free of charge to citizens who do not speak Uzbek" [9]. In the 1995 edition, the text is very abbreviated: "the study of the state language is carried out by the citizens of Bapul. This article plays an extremely important role in the development of the state language policy in society aimed at attracting national minorities to the study of the state language.

In the new edition, the text of some large-scale articles of the previous law is divided into two parts, and the expression of meaning is also more specifically embodied. If we look at article 13 of the 1989 Law on the choice of language in education, it consists of three paragraphs. In the 1995 edition, this article is presented in two articles. Article 5: "in the Republic of Uzbekistan, organizations operating in the state language, in places where national groups live closely, the activities of preschool organizations are provided in their language." Article 6: "Persons residing in the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to freely choose the language of instruction" [9]. This article can be considered as one of the distinctive features of a democratic and rule-of-law State, which has opened up many opportunities for national minorities.

Article 15 of the first law was directly relevant to the Ministry of Secondary and Secondary Special and Higher Education, which emphasizes the issue of studying the state language in secondary, special and higher educational institutions of non-unique groups, this article was shortened in the subsequent edition, since its content is directly related to the riddles of these ministries.

In the 25th article of the previous law, the method of writing the surname and surname is mentioned in detail. In the 15th article of the later law, its text is expressed very briefly: "people living in the Republic of Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality, first name, patronymic and surname, have the right to write in accordance with national historical traditions" [9]. Of course, the democratic trend is observed here, and to this day, along with the national surname, the Russian surname and surname continue. In our opinion, the rejection of the Russian surname will be a serious obstacle to the development of the state language.

The 27th article of the previous law, responsibility for language matters, was framed and compiled from a long text similar to the interpretation of the law. In the subsequent edition, the same meaning is briefly expressed: "in the Uzbek Republic, an obscene or hostile view of the state or other languages is prohibited. Persons who hinder the

intergovernmental appeal of citizens, the free right to choose a language in education and upbringing, comply with the law”[9]. This article warns that it is impossible to unknowingly interfere in the linguistic interaction of national minorities and their education in their native language, because there is a possibility of a national conflict due to interference in this issue, and in a country where national values, including the languages of all our indigenous peoples, are protected on the basis of democratic tendencies, should only contribute to their development.

When comparing the 1989 law with the 1995 version, it again becomes clear that some articles of the law, the text of which was formulated very specifically, received a detailed form in their wording. For example, article 29 stated: “the areas in which the state language officially operates, the Uzbek literary language is fully subject to scientific laws and rules”[9]. This article of the 7th edition of 1995 mentions in more detail: "in circles where the state language officially operates, the Uzbek literary language is observed in accordance with the current rules and regulations. The state ensures the improvement and enrichment of the Uzbek language, including through the introduction of recognized scientific, technical and socio-political terminology” [9]. It is worth mentioning here that in the first years of independence, terms were used that either were not scientifically justified, and in their use, the ichthyification of scientists was observed. Editing this article requires that not every organization arbitrarily came up with a term and presented it. That is, terminology is recommended by the terminology committee only after it has been justified.

A very interesting point is that in the 1995 edition of the 16th article of the previous law, in which the native alphabet (Uzbek Jesuvia) was removed as a separate discipline in secondary and special and higher Makobits. There is no need to explain the importance of knowing this line, but this question is expressed in the law of the person “on the introduction of the Uzbek line and the Latinized alphabet”, article 2.

Another abridged article is the 4th article of the previous law, the content of which is not visible in the 1995 edition. This article stated: "In the Republic of Uzbekistan, heads of government bodies and officials of state power need to know the state language adequately to perform their official duties. Persons providing services to the population, depending on their activities, need knowledge of the state language to perform their official duties”[9]. The reduction of this article negates the compulsion to know the state language from persons directly engaged in activities in state bodies, authorities and the service sector. When the leader does not feel this responsibility, that is, knowledge of the state language, he begins to act in the language that he wants and knows, and his servants will also be invalidated on this issue. Therefore, this issue is expressed in the ”Concept of improving the language policy and development of the Uzbek language in 2020-2030“, chapter 3, as shown below: "coercion to adequate knowledge of the state language and to

it in a respectful attitude to the heads and officials of state organizations and bodies. All state organizations and bodies employ qualified personnel who have the right to work in the state language”” Since this material covers a certain stage, it is advisable to include this material in the resolution of the law.

The procedure for the enactment of the law “On the State Language” was signed by the resolution of the Majlisi Oli of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 1995 under the number 168-1, according to which all articles of the law, with the exception of articles 9 and 10, entered into force from the date of its publication and have been fully taken into account in the practice of articles 9 and 10 since 2005 year.

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers “On Amendments and Additions to the “State Program for the implementation of the Law” The Uzbek SSR On the State language” dated September 10, 1996 is signed under the number 311.

32 years have passed since the adoption of the law “On the State Language”, and 27 years have passed since its later revision, and until today there have been radical changes in the political and social life of the world community, including Uzbekistan. The XXI century has turned into the age of information and globalization, where not all previously adopted laws of the 90s meet the requirements of modernity. From this point of view, the new version of the law “On the State Language” is a requirement of the time, and, as we all know, the new version of the law "On the State Language" of 7 chapters and 29 articles has been developed and adapted to the articles 2, 7, 8, 10, 13, 16, 20, 21 and 24 made changes and approved by the Senate of the Majlisi Oli and the President of the person Sh.M.Mirziyoyev is pending.

The development of the state in society is closely related to the stability of laws. In a society where there are all stable laws, its widespread development is also observed. Non-compliance or non-compliance with the law is a crime. In the personal law” About the state language " responsibility for non-compliance with its articles was ignored. Therefore, problems and problems arise for the development of the state language and the implementation in practice of the law “On the State language”, which can also be called evidence of misunderstanding of the law “On the state language”. For example, in 2019, rumors spread in periodicals and social networks[11] that the Russian language in Uzbekistan would be upgraded to the status of the state language. The plaintiffs cite examples in several states where two or three languages are active as the state language. Russian Russian, however, should not be forgotten that in the environment in which we live, if the Russian language is given a state status along with Uzbek, bilingualism develops, and Uzbek remains in the shadow of the Russian language.

In refuting these rumors, scientists and intellectuals of the country have spoken out and proved that this is impossible in the Uzbek environment.

To restore the nation, language and other national values in the expression of the First President of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov, "it is necessary to raise the legal culture of our people to the level of state policy. Because the concept of tar independence itself also represents a wide range of nuances. That is, independence means not only freedom, a sense of free life, but also the conscious right to make one's own destiny." [12.P.27]. The sovereignty state has put our destiny in its own hands, the protection of the national language is also in our hands.

In short, the role of the Law of Uzbekistan "on the State language" during the 32 years of its existence has no equal in restoring political, social, spiritual life and the revival of national and cultural values of the multinational people of Uzbekistan. This law is considered the main principle of the independence of the state, self-knowledge and national identity of the people of Uzbekistan. This law and the achievement of this post were dreamed of by our ancestors. The ascent of the Uzbek language to the highest state position should be the pride of all Uzbek and Uzbek peoples. It is this law that has led to the fact that the state language policy will be fairly implemented in society and will maintain a stable situation with other languages in society. The opportunities that this law has brought for the development of the national languages of the indigenous people and their diaspora are completely absent in the laws of other Commonwealth States. This is evidenced by the activities of secondary and higher educational institutions in non-State languages, the activities of national centers, national media in minority languages. According to him, openness, which is one of the noble qualities of Uzbeks and Uzbeks, has also found its embodiment in this law. In order to further improve and edit this law and the development of the state language, giving special importance to the following points will contribute not only to the development of the state language, but also to the further improvement of the language situation in the country.

- Attention should be paid to the language and style of the law;
- It is necessary to increase the requirements for the norms of the literary language;
- the riddles of writing and spelling must be solved from a scientific and legal point of view;
- the promotion of the state language, as a spiritual and educational work, should increase not only on the Day of the State language, but also constantly.
- Innovative and interactive methods should be established in the teaching of the state language.
- cases of using the state and other national languages should be expressed more specifically.
- so that the purity of the language from any elevations is reflected in the law, so that the use of terms is developed and put into operation on the basis of certain norms.

- the important points that exist in the decisions on the development of the state language, the program for the development of the state language and require constant compliance with deadlines will be taken into account in the articles of the Alhida law, it would be better;

- internalization of the state language and improvement of the quality of translation;
- Regularly publish the magazine "Dalat Tili"

The State language is also one of the main and symbolic pillars of the state. To express the great is the spirit of the nation. As long as Uzbekistan is sovereign, regardless of how people react to the law "On the State Language" and other normative acts related to the language, the state language will remain a symbol of the state and the spirit of the nation.

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